

ISic2944

I.Sicily inscription 2944

Language

Latin

Type

(?)

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Segesta

Place of origin (modern)

Segesta

Provenance

From interior wall above case Barbaro

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Segesta, excavation stores, inventory SG2006

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---]poliη[---]

Apparatus

Text of Ampolo and Erdas 2019

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644853

Bibliography

Nenci, G. 1991. Florilegio epigrafico segestano. *Annali della scuola normale superiore di Pisa*. 21: 920-929. At 928 no.9 ph

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Ampolo, Carmine, Erdas, Donatella 2019. *Inscriptiones Segestanae*. Le iscrizioni

greche e latine di Segesta. Pisa. At L7

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